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The Worsening of the Condition of Women Employed with Preschool Children in the Italian Regions in the Period 2015-2019

Campania in 2019 has the lowest value among the Italian regions of the employment rate of women with preschool children as a percentage of employed women without children, or equal to 55.9%.

Istat calculates the value of the variable "Ratio between the employment rates (25-49 years) of women with preschool children and women without children". This variable is present in the ISTAT-BES computed for the period 2004-2019. The variable calculated as follows: "Employment rate of women aged 25-49 with at least one child aged 0-5 on the employment rate of women aged 25-49 without children per 100." To simplify the following, this variable will be indicated with the following acronym: DCFP / DSF.

The ranking of the Italian regions by value of the DCFP / DSF in 2019. Marche is in first place by value of DCFP / DSF with an amount equal to 95.00% in 2019, followed by Abruzzo with an amount equal to 86.20% and from the Aosta Valley with a value of 85.8%. In the middle of the table there are Emilia Romagna with an amount equal to 81.10%, Basilicata with a value equal to 80.9% and Molise with an amount equal to 80.8%. Trentino Alto Adige closes the ranking with an amount equal to 72.5%, Sicily with an amount equal to 65.9% and Campania with a value equal to 55.90%.

The ranking of the Italian regions by value of the DCFP / DSF by variation in the period 2004-2019. Sardinia is in first place for variation in the value of DCFP / DSF in the period between 2004 and 2019 with a value of 19.3, followed by Basilicata with an amount of 17.6 and Marche with a value of 16. , 7. In the middle of the table there are Valle d'Aosta with an amount equal to 5, Piedmont with a value equal to 4.4 and Veneto with an amount equal to 1.9. Emilia Romagna closes the ranking with an amount equal to -3.1, Calabria with a value equal to -6.5 and Campania with a value equal to 7.8.

North. The value of the DCFP / DSF in the North decreased in the period between 2015 and 2019 going from an amount of 83.30 to a value of 81.10 or a variation of -2.20 units equal to a variation of -2.64%. In the transition between 2015 and 2016 the value of the DCFP / DSF decreased from an amount equal to 83.30 to a value equal to 80.60 or a change equal to an amount of -2.70 units equal to a value of -3.24%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the amount of the DCFP / DSF in Northern Italy increased from an amount equal to 80.60 units up to a value equal to 80.80 units or equal to a variation of 0, 20 units equal to a value of 0.25%. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of DCFP / DSF in Northern Italy decreased from an amount of 80.80 to a value of 80.50 or a variation of -0.30 equivalent to a value of -0 , 37%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019 the value of the DCFP / DSF increased from an amount equal to 80.50 units up to a value equal to 81.10 units equal to a value of 0.60 units equivalent to a variation of 0 , 75%.

Center. The value of the DCFP / DSF in Central Italy decreased in the period between 2015 and 2016 going from an amount equal to 82.70 to a value equal to 83.70 units or equal to a variation of 1.00 units equal to an amount of 1.21%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the amount of the DCFP / DSF decreased from an amount equal to 83.70 to a value equal to 80.70 units or equal to a variation of -3.00 units equivalent to a variation of -3.58%. In the transition between 2017 and 2018, the value of the DCFP / DSF in Central Italy increased from an amount equal to 80.70 units up

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to a value equal to 81.60 units or equal to a change of 0.90 units equal to a change of 1.12%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019 the value of the DCFP / DSF increased from an amount equal to 81.60 units up to a value equal to 81.70 units or equal to a change of 0.10 units equivalent to a change in 0.12%. Overall, in the period considered, the value of DCFP / DSF decreased by 1 unit, equal to a variation of -1.21%.

South of Italy. The value of the DCFP / DSF decreased in the South between 2015 and 2019 from an amount of 73.50 to a value of 66.80 or a change of -6.70 units equal to an amount of -9.12%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017 the value of the DCFP / DSF decreased from an amount equal to 73.50 units up to a value equal to 71.30 units or a change equal to a value of -2.20 units equal to an amount of -2.29%. In the transition between 2016 and 2017, the value of DCFP / DSF remained constant at a value of 71.30. Between 2017 and 2018 the value of DCFP / DSF decreased from an amount of 71.30 units to a value of 65.30 units or a variation of -6.00 units equivalent to a variation of -8.42%. In the transition between 2018 and 2019 the value of the amount of the DCFP / DSF increased from an amount of 65.30 units up to a value of 66.80 units equal to a change of 1.50 units equal to a value of 2.30%.

Clusterization. To verify the presence of groupings also called clusters among the Italian regions about the variable of interest, a clustering activity was carried out using the k-Means algorithm and representation with t-SNE algorithms. The algorithm has identified the presence of 2 clusters, namely:

- Cluster 1: Abruzzo, Emilia-Romagna, Friuli-Venezia Giulia, Lazio, Liguria, Lombardy, Marche, Molise, Piedmont, Sardinia, Tuscany, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta, Veneto;
- Cluster 2: Basilicata, Calabria, Campania, Puglia, Sicily, Trentino-Alto Adige.

The data show the presence of two clusters of which the first is substantially coincident with the Center-North with higher levels of DCFP / DSF while the second tends to coincide with the South with a low level of DCFP / DSF. Trentino-Alto Adige is an exception in the second cluster, which therefore, from the point of view of the variable of interest, performs as a southern region.

Conclusions. In summary, the observed variable represents the ability of women with preschool children to be employed in work activities compared to childless women. The data generally show a worsening of the working conditions of women with preschool children compared to women without children in Italy and in the various Italian macro-regions in the period 2015-2019. The situation is particularly serious in Southern Italy where on average 7 women with children are employed for every 10 women without children, and especially in Campania where 56 women with preschool children work for every 100 women without children. The data therefore shows the failure of the economic policies of gender equality and the lack of adequate services capable of allowing women with preschool children an adequate participation in the labor market on a regional basis.

Declarations

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References

Leogrando, Angelo. Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. No. 112801. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Leogrando, Angelo. The Mental Health Index in the Italian Regions. No. 112954. University Library of Munich, Germany, 2022.

Laureti, L., Costantiello, A., & Leogrando, A. (2022). Satisfaction with the Environmental Condition in the Italian Regions between 2004 and 2020. Available at SSRN 4061708.

Leogrando, A., Costantiello, A., Laureti, L., & Leogrando, D. (2021). *The Determinants of Landscape and Cultural Heritage Among Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019* (No. 110814). University Library of Munich, Germany.

Magazzino, C., & Leogrando, A. (2021). Subjective Well-Being in Italian Regions: A Panel Data Approach. *Applied Econometrics and International Development*, 21(1), 1-18.

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Avoidable Mortality in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6551666>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Risk of Poverty in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6194023>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Employment Rate in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6211793>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Duration of Civil Proceedings in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6188615>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Reduction of NEETs in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6212291>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Social Participation in the Italian Regions. In *Il Sud Est*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6212069>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Crowding of Prisons in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6395200>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Mortality from Cancer in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590380>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Mortality from Nervous System Diseases in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591151>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Healthy Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6484049>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Multichronicity in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591360>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Life Expectancy at Birth in the Italian Regions. *Il Sud Est*, <https://ilsudest.it/>. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6469551>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Childhood Mortality in Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590870>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Life Expectancy Without Limitations in Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6591546>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Mortality from Road Accidents in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6590888>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Excess Weight in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6635645>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Percentage of Smokers in the Italian Regions. International Web Post. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6636122>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Sedentary Lifestyle in Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6661189>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Adequate Nutrition in the Italian regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6743234>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Graduates in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6790391>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Income Gap Between Northern and Southern Italy. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013650>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Clustering and Prediction of the Employment Rate in the Italian Regions in the Period 2004-2019. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013660>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). Reduction of the Perception of Employment Insecurity in the Italian Regions between 2013 and 2019. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013700>

Angelo Leogrando. (2022). The Satisfaction for the Work in the Italian Regions. Il Sud Est. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7013706>

Appendix

Rapporto tra i tassi di occupazione (25-49 anni) delle donne con figli in età prescolare e delle donne senza figli nel 2019

Rank	Regione	%
1	Marche	★ 95,0
2	Abruzzo	★ 86,2
3	Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	★ 85,8
4	Umbria	★ 85,5
5	Piemonte	★ 84,3
6	Lombardia	★ 82,7
7	Toscana	★ 82,4
8	Liguria	★ 81,3
9	Emilia-Romagna	★ 81,1
10	Basilicata	★ 80,9
11	Molise	★ 80,8
11	Sardegna	★ 80,8
12	Lazio	★ 77,8
13	Veneto	★ 77,6
14	Friuli-Venezia Giulia	★ 77,0
15	Calabria	★ 75,9
16	Puglia	★ 74,5
17	Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	★ 72,5
18	Sicilia	★ 65,9
19	Campania	★ 55,9

	Rapporto tra i tassi di occupazione (25-49 anni) delle donne con figli in età prescolare e delle donne senza figli																Var Assoluta	Var %
	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2004-2019	2004-2019
Piemonte	79,9	76	81,1	81,2	81,5	83	82,3	81,6	82,4	84,5	82,3	82	80,2	83,5	86	84,3	4,4	5,51
Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste	80,8	84,6	80,6	77	82,8	77,4	78,2	82,7	86,6	85	79	78,4	84,9	87,7	88	85,8	5	6,19
Liguria	80,1	74,9	84,9	86,5	82,1	83,5	84	79,2	78	89,7	85,9	89	81,1	84,6	81,2	81,3	1,2	1,50
Lombardia	75,7	74,5	76,2	76,9	78,9	78,6	77,3	76,1	78,8	78,5	79,4	81,5	78,7	79	78,6	82,7	7	9,25
Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol	72,2	72,6	68,5	68,9	68	69,6	66,8	69,7	72,6	74,5	77,1	78,5	79,6	72	73,5	72,5	0,3	0,42
Veneto	75,7	76,4	79,2	76,6	76,3	81,3	79,2	80,4	80	78,6	87,6	89,3	86,1	82,1	76,9	77,6	1,9	2,51
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	79,5	84,6	77,1	85,8	86,7	86,2	79	83,9	81,9	79,8	88,7	78,2	75,1	78,4	80,9	77	-2,5	-3,14
Emilia-Romagna	84,2	86,5	81,6	84,6	81,3	87,4	85,8	82,5	84,3	80,7	77,7	83,5	81,3	81,9	84,5	81,1	-3,1	-3,68
Toscana	81,3	81,4	78,2	78,6	87	81,1	79,4	80,1	85,9	84,4	92	85,7	89,4	85,3	83	82,4	1,1	1,35
Umbria	83,8	95	87,8	84,2	81	84,7	78,7	78,3	84,7	92,2	85,5	83,4	85,3	78,4	80,4	85,5	1,7	2,03
Marche	78,3	84,6	83,6	83,4	86,7	88	84,9	81,6	81,7	81,8	83,9	85,4	77,9	76,3	83,7	95	16,7	21,33
Lazio	71,7	71,1	72,5	73,8	72,2	77,1	76,9	74,7	74,5	80,1	81,3	80,3	81,4	79,2	80,2	77,8	6,1	8,51
Abruzzo	74,3	77,9	76,9	76,8	83,9	80,2	71,7	77,6	81,9	93	90,7	95,4	74	81,9	78,6	86,2	11,9	16,02
Molise	73	82,6	70,7	84,9	84,2	78,7	79,1	85,5	79,4	65,2	70,4	71,3	80,8	77,5	89	80,8	7,8	10,68
Campania	63,7	63,3	65,4	58,6	58,3	61,7	63,3	62,8	69,3	66,8	69,6	71	70	63,5	57,4	55,9	-7,8	-12,24
Puglia	66,2	68,7	62,5	64,6	70,6	64,7	60,9	78,9	76,1	70,2	81,6	73,4	74,5	79,9	75,1	74,5	8,3	12,54
Basilicata	63,3	65,9	68,7	69	70,9	72,7	83,3	79,6	77	69,2	80,9	80,3	69,7	72,6	71,6	80,9	17,6	27,80
Calabria	82,4	79,7	71	61,6	78,2	72	74,1	70,3	72,5	83,2	80,9	67,3	62,4	63,5	59,4	75,9	-6,5	-7,89
Sicilia	65,8	70	67,5	63,8	62,9	59,2	58	63,9	67,1	64,9	67,3	77	76,3	76,4	63,4	65,9	0,1	0,15
Sardegna	61,5	64,9	75,8	79,8	76,9	79,9	68,9	73,9	88	74,2	80,8	80,6	83,2	78,4	78,6	80,8	19,3	31,38
Nord	78	77,4	78,5	79,3	79,3	81,3	79,7	78,9	80,4	80,3	81,6	83,3	80,6	80,8	80,5	81,1	3,1	3,97
Centro	76,2	77,5	76,6	77,1	79,1	80,1	78,9	77,6	79,8	82,6	85,1	82,7	83,7	80,7	81,6	81,7	5,5	7,22
Mezzogiorno	65,2	67,3	66,3	64	66,1	64,2	62	67,5	71,6	69,8	73,4	73,5	71,3	71,3	65,3	66,8	1,6	2,45
Italia	69,5	69,7	70,6	70,9	72,4	73,3	71,7	72,4	75,1	75,4	77,5	77,8	76	75,5	73,8	74,3	4,8	6,91

Rapporto tra i tassi di occupazione (25-49 anni) delle donne con figli in età prescolare e delle donne senza figli

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2015-2019
Nord	★ 83,30	★ 80,60	★ 80,80	★ 80,50	★ 81,10	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		☆ -2,70	☆ 0,20	☆ -0,30	☆ 0,60	☆ -2,20
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		☆ -3,24	☆ 0,25	☆ -0,37	☆ 0,75	☆ -2,64
Centro	★ 82,70	★ 83,70	★ 80,70	★ 81,60	★ 81,70	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		☆ 1,00	☆ -3,00	☆ 0,90	☆ 0,10	☆ -1,00
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		☆ 1,21	☆ -3,58	☆ 1,12	☆ 0,12	☆ -1,21
Mezzogiorno	★ 73,50	★ 71,30	★ 71,30	★ 65,30	★ 66,80	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		☆ -2,20	☆ 0,00	★ -6,00	☆ 1,50	★ -6,70
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		☆ -2,99	☆ 0,00	★ -8,42	☆ 2,30	★ -9,12
Italia	★ 77,80	★ 76,00	★ 75,50	★ 73,80	★ 74,30	
<i>Variazione assoluta</i>		☆ -1,80	☆ -0,50	☆ -1,70	☆ 0,50	☆ -3,50
<i>Variazione percentuale</i>		☆ -2,31	☆ -0,66	☆ -2,25	☆ 0,68	☆ -4,50

	2019	Regione	Cluster	Silhouette
13	86.2	Abruzzo	C1	0.627612
8	81.1	Emilia-Romagna	C1	0.666772
7	77.0	Friuli-Venezia G...	C1	0.653667
12	77.8	Lazio	C1	0.554343
3	81.3	Liguria	C1	0.663087
4	82.7	Lombardia	C1	0.619749
11	95.0	Marche	C1	0.666701
14	80.8	Molise	C1	0.582993
1	84.3	Piemonte	C1	0.672717
20	80.8	Sardegna	C1	0.561292
9	82.4	Toscana	C1	0.66249
10	85.5	Umbria	C1	0.654445
2	85.8	Valle d'Aosta/V...	C1	0.657622
6	77.6	Veneto	C1	0.649573
17	80.9	Basilicata	C2	0.540144
18	75.9	Calabria	C2	0.567383
15	55.9	Campania	C2	0.642562
16	74.5	Puglia	C2	0.588302
19	65.9	Sicilia	C2	0.632983
5	72.5	Trentino-Alto A...	C2	0.587665

Rapporto tra i tassi di occupazione (25-49 anni) delle donne con figli in età prescolare e delle donne senza figli variazione assoluta

Rank	Regions	2004-2019
1	<i>Sardegna</i>	19,3
2	<i>Basilicata</i>	17,6
3	<i>Marche</i>	16,7
4	<i>Abruzzo</i>	11,9
5	<i>Puglia</i>	8,3
6	<i>Molise</i>	7,8
7	<i>Lombardia</i>	7
8	<i>Lazio</i>	6,1
9	<i>Valle d'Aosta/Vallée d'Aoste</i>	5
10	<i>Piemonte</i>	4,4
11	<i>Veneto</i>	1,9
12	<i>Umbria</i>	1,7
13	<i>Liguria</i>	1,2
14	<i>Toscana</i>	1,1
15	<i>Trentino-Alto Adige/Südtirol</i>	0,3
16	<i>Sicilia</i>	0,1
17	<i>Friuli-Venezia Giulia</i>	-2,5
18	<i>Emilia-Romagna</i>	-3,1
19	<i>Calabria</i>	-6,5
20	<i>Campania</i>	-7,8

Rapporto tra i tassi di occupazione (25-49 anni) delle donne con figli in età prescolare e delle donne senza figli

	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019
Nord	83,30	80,60	80,80	80,50	81,10
Centro	82,70	83,70	80,70	81,60	81,70
Mezzogiorno	73,50	71,30	71,30	65,30	66,80
Italia	77,80	76,00	75,50	73,80	74,30

